

Workplace Ostracism and Employee Retention: A Mediation Model

Abstract

Purpose: This study aims to examine the influence of workplace ostracism on core self-evaluation, counterproductive work behavior, and employee retention in private sector organizations in Saudi Arabia. It addresses two gaps in the current literature: The need for research on workplace ostracism in the Saudi Arabian context and the understanding of the interrelationships between employee retention, core self-evaluation, and counterproductive work behavior in the context of workplace ostracism.

Methodology: In this study, a survey was held for native Arabic speakers. The back-to-back method was used for the translation of the questionnaire. The translated questionnaire was pilot tested with a small group to ensure clarity and suitability for. The data were collected in three phases using an online platform.

Findings: The results of the study show that respondents have low workplace ostracism and counterproductive work behavior, whereas they exhibit high core self-evaluation and employee retention. The results also indicate that core self-evaluation has the strongest and most positive relation with employee retention while negative relation with counterproductive work behavior.

Keywords: Workplace ostracism; Employee retention; Core self-evaluation; Counterproductive work behavior

INTRODUCTION

Workplace ostracism, the practice of being excluded, ignored, or socially isolated by colleagues, has emerged as a critical issue in the modern-day workplace. With people spending considerable time at work, social interactions with peers and superiors can significantly shape their workplace experiences. The widespread nature of workplace ostracism has made it a growing worry for researchers, organizations, and employees alike (Wang, 2022). The phenomenon's negative impact on individuals can be long-lasting, ranging from job dissatisfaction, psychological distress, reduced job performance, and decreased organizational commitment. Beyond the individual level, workplace ostracism can profoundly influence organizations, leading to decreased

productivity, increased turnover rates, and lower morale. As such, addressing workplace ostracism is vital to promote a healthy and inclusive work environment that benefits individuals and organizations. (Li *et al.*, 2021)

As an interpersonal stressor, workplace ostracism jeopardizes individuals' social resources, which are assets that can be used to solve problems or deal with challenging events as needed (Choi, 2020). Therefore, when people perceive a probable or actual loss of these important resources, they view it as a threat. Resource loss events are responsible for most cases of depression (Hobfoll, 1989). workplace ostracism significantly limits the resources that a person can keep. When ostracized people use their social resources to combat exclusion, they are less likely to replenish those resources like others, which causes their reserves to run low (Carter-Sowell, 2016). Those who lack resources may feel stressed and exhausted since resources can help someone manage daily chores. Even though both sexes can be a victim of workplace ostracism, for example, research reveals female faculty members perceive workplace ostracism more than males (Zimmerman *et al.*, 2016).

The impact of workplace ostracism can also be seen in other aspects. When employees experience workplace ostracism can lead to exhaustion and the depletion of their psychological, emotional, and material resources (Ferris *et al.*, 2008). This passive interpersonal interaction can negatively impact employees' psychological state and behavior patterns, decreasing participation, concentration, commitment, dedication, responsibility, and emotional dependence on the organization and others (Chi & Liang, 2013). Ostracized employees may also experience negative attitudes and retaliatory behavior, inhibiting the generation and implementation of innovative ideas. Previous research suggests that knowledge hiding and organizational identification may mediate the relationship between workplace ostracism and these behavioral patterns and psychological states (Wang *et al.*, 2021).

The purpose of the study is to find the influence of workplace ostracism on core self-evaluation, counterproductive work behavior and employee retention in the private sector organizations of Saudi Arabia. The present study aims to address two significant gaps in the current literature. The first is a population gap, with more research on workplace ostracism in Saudi Arabia. Despite the prevalence of this issue in many workplaces worldwide, there is still a need for research to understand how it manifests in the Saudi Arabian context, where cultural and social norms may differ from those in other countries. The second gap is a theoretical gap in the

understanding of the relationship between employee retention, core self-evaluation, and counterproductive work behavior. For instance, empirical evidence has shown the relationship between workplace ostracism and counterproductive work behavior (Zhu & Zhang, 2021) and the relationship between workplace ostracism, core self-evaluation, and self-esteem (Ferris *et al.*, 2015). While previous studies have examined the impact of workplace ostracism on these variables independently, there needs to be more research that considers how they may be interrelated. Addressing these gaps can contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of workplace ostracism and its impact on individuals and organizations in Saudi Arabia, ultimately leading to the development of effective interventions to prevent and address this issue. The study also includes investigating the impact of workplace ostracism on employee retention, core self-evaluation, and counterproductive work behavior. This study aims to contribute to the literature on workplace ostracism and its impact on important organizational outcomes, such as employee retention and counterproductive work behavior.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Workplace ostracism is a type of social exclusion that occurs when an employee is intentionally ignored, excluded, or overlooked by their colleagues or superiors in the workplace (Bedi, 2021). It can take many forms, including being left out of meetings, not being invited to social events or activities, receiving the cold shoulder, or being given silent treatment (Howard *et al.*, 2020). As a behavior that violates social-ethical norms and harms victims, workplace ostracism involves major ethical issues in organizations. According to research, ostracism in the workplace can be severely detrimental to psychological and work-related outcomes, as it can lead to improved levels of job stress and emotional burnout (Wu *et al.*, 2012), increased counterproductive work behavior (Yang & Treadway, 2016), decreased performance engagement (Ferris *et al.*, 2015), decreased citizenship behavior (Wu *et al.*, 2016), and suppression of prosocial behavior (Balliet & Ferris, 2013). It can lead to loneliness, isolation, and low self-esteem, negatively impacting mental and physical health and job performance (Bellou, 2016). Over time, workplace ostracism can lead to reduced job satisfaction and retention (Wu *et al.*, 2016).

Employee Retention

Employee retention is defined as an organization's efforts to encourage and recognize current employees so they will stay on staff in the future (Gabriel *et al.*, 2022). Retention reduces

hiring and training costs and maintains a stable workforce, which boosts output, morale, and success (Khalid & Nawab, 2018).

Workplace ostracism and employee retention have a close connection. Employees who feel isolated or abandoned by coworkers may feel lonely, frustrated, and stressed (O'Reilly et al., 2015). These feelings lower job satisfaction and increase turnover. Employees will be happier at work and stay longer if they feel valued and supported by their coworkers and the organization. According to studies (Zhang et al., 2019; Van Zelderren, 2022), workplace ostracism employees are likelier to quit their jobs voluntarily.

The social exchange theory states that employees trade their skills, time, and effort for pay, benefits, and job security (Balu, 1964; Oberai et al., 2021). Socioemotional resources are symbolic and particularistic, while economic resources are material possessions used to meet financial needs (Balkin & Werner, 2023). Social exchange relationships foster positive interpersonal connections (Stafford & Kuiper, 2021). Isolated employees may think they need to get the organization's benefits, which can reduce their desire to stay (Wu *et al.*, 2016).

Workplace ostracism is a bad social interaction that makes a person feel unwelcome in the organization and separates them from it (Dash *et al.*, 2023). Workplace ostracism may reduce job embeddedness or a person's integration into their employer (Lyu *et al.*, 2019). The job embeddedness theory states that employee perceptions and the workplace environment affect job attachment, which affects ER (Halvorsen et al., 2015).

H₁: Workplace ostracism has a direct and significant impact on employee retention.

Core Self-Evaluation

Core self-evaluation is a psychological term for a person's overall assessment of themselves (Ding & Lin, 2020). It is a person's core beliefs about their value, skill, and power to influence their environment. It includes self-esteem, locus of control, emotional stability, and generalized self-evaluation (An *et al.*, 2021). These four elements are called "core self-evaluation" because they are foundational and crucial to self-evaluation (Munn & James, 2022). Higher core self-evaluation levels are associated with better mental health, job satisfaction, and academic and professional success (Munn & James, 2022; Ding & Lin, 2020). High core self-evaluation scores are associated with optimism, self-control, and resilience. Low core self-evaluation may lead to more stress, anxiety, and self-doubt (Wang & Xu, 2019).

Workplace Ostracism and Core Self Evaluation

Core self-evaluation can affect how individuals respond to workplace ostracism (Wang *et al.*, 2021). Individuals with high levels of core self-evaluation tend to have a more positive self-concept and a greater sense of self-worth. As a result, they may be better equipped to cope with the negative impact of workplace ostracism (Shemesh & Heiman, 2021).

Research has shown that individuals with high levels of core self-evaluation are less likely to experience negative emotions due to workplace ostracism (Turkoglu & Dalgic, 2019). This is because individuals with high core self-evaluation tend to have a more positive self-image and are less likely to base their self-worth on external validation from others (Gu, 2021). As a result, they may be less likely to interpret workplace ostracism as a reflection of their worth and better equipped to cope with the negative feelings associated with ostracism (Huertas-Valdivia *et al.*, 2019). In contrast, individuals with low levels of core self-evaluation may be more vulnerable to the negative effects of workplace ostracism (Tu *et al.*, 2019). They may be more likely to feel rejected and isolated and may experience a greater impact on their self-esteem, job satisfaction, and overall well-being (Van Zelderren *et al.*, 2022). This can decrease job performance, retention, and other negative outcomes (Turkoglu & Dalgic, 2019).

H₂: Workplace ostracism has a direct and significant impact on core self-evaluation.

Employees with high core self-evaluation are more likely to have a positive attitude toward their job and the organization and are, therefore, more likely to stay with the organization longer (Zhang *et al.*, 2020; Chhabra, 2020). Additionally, employees with high core self-evaluation are often more confident in their abilities and are more likely to take on challenging tasks and seek out opportunities for growth and development within the organization (Joo & Jo, 2017). This can lead to a sense of career progression and personal fulfillment, which can contribute to retention (Tian *et al.*, 2021).

According to social exchange theory, individuals with high core self-evaluation are likelier to interact positively with their colleagues and supervisors (Ahn *et al.*, 2018). Positive relationships with others in the workplace create a sense of community and belonging, which can increase the likelihood of retention (Randel *et al.*, 2018). Moreover, job embeddedness theory suggests that individuals with high core self-evaluation are more likely to have deep roots in their organization, making it harder for them to leave (Qazi *et al.*, 2015). They may have strong connections with

their coworkers, feel invested in their work, and have a sense of fit with the organization's culture (Holtom & Darabi, 2018).

H₃: Core self-evaluation has a direct and significant impact on employee retention.

Workplace Ostracism, Core Self-Evaluation, and Employee Retention

Employees who experience workplace ostracism may perceive their core self-evaluation as threatened, leading to reduced self-esteem and motivation to stay with the organization (Zhang *et al.*, 2023; Wang *et al.*, 2021). In addition, individuals with low core self-evaluation may be more susceptible to the negative effects of workplace ostracism. They may begin to doubt their value and competence, leading to lower self-esteem and a decrease in their overall well-being (Sarwar *et al.*, 2017). Conversely, employees with high core self-evaluation may be better equipped to handle workplace ostracism, as they may have greater resilience (Oh, 2022).

Social exchange theory suggests that employees engage in social interactions to obtain rewards and avoid punishment (Balu, 1964). Workplace ostracism can be seen as a form of punishment, and when employees feel excluded or ignored, they may question their value and worth to the organization (Khushk *et al.*, 2022). This can lead to decreased organizational commitment and a lower likelihood of staying in the organization (Wang *et al.*, 2022).

H₄: The relationship between workplace ostracism and employee retention is mediated by core self-evaluation.

Counterproductive Work Behavior

Ali *et al.* (2022) defines counterproductive work behavior as willful negligence that hinders an organization's efficiency. Employees intentionally undermine the organization's goals, performance, and process. It includes bullying, harassment, theft, fraud, sabotage, tardiness, and absences (Amalia & Zakiy, 2021). Counterproductive work behavior can result from job insecurity, leadership support, coworker support, low job satisfaction, and organizational injustice (Bilal *et al.*, 2020). Unchecked can create a hostile workplace and moral and legal issues (Holland & Thynne, 2022). Employees may lose their jobs and reputations. Guilt, worry, and stress can harm employees (De Clercq *et al.*, 2022). Counterproductive work behavior can make coworkers tense, anxious, and distrustful (Namubiru, 2023).

Workplace Ostracism and Counterproductive Work Behavior

Workplace ostracism exposure can result in counterproductive work behavior in several ways (Amalia & Zakiy, 2021; Bilal *et al.*, 2020; Namubiru, 2023). Isolated employees may lose

interest in the organization, lose motivation to do good work, and fail to uphold organizational values and standards (Van Zelder et al., 2022). Counterproductive work behavior (Sowe & Arslan, 2023). These employees can commit theft or sabotage to retaliate against the organization or coworkers. They may spread rumors or chitchat to show their power (Bashir et al., 2020). According to social exchange theory, employees who experience workplace ostracism may feel mistreated and turn to counterproductive work behavior for redress (Blau, 1964; Ali & Johl, 2020). Counterproductive work behavior may compensate for the organization's lack of resources and social support (Jahanzeb et al., 2022).

H₅: Workplace ostracism has a direct and significant impact on counterproductive work behavior.

Counterproductive Work Behavior and Employee Retention

A reduction in employee retention may result from counterproductive work behavior. It can damage the organizational reputation, lower morale, and encourage others to do the same (Griep et al., 2021). Employee dissatisfaction may lead to an unfavorable feedback loop that lowers retention rates (Murad et al., 2021). Employees who want to quit their jobs frequently exhibit counterproductive work behavior (Chang et al., 2013). Due to procedural issues, employees who want to resign must prove their intentions through attendance and late assignments. Employee intent to leave predicts counterproductive work behavior (Cohen et al., 2013). Since their relationship is inversed and counterproductive work behavior decreases with employee retention, keeping employees can solve it. Employee retention increases compassion and respect (Akosile, 2022).

H₆: Counterproductive work behavior directly and significantly impacts employee retention.

Workplace ostracism significantly predicts counterproductive work behavior (Steffens et al., 2021; Howard et al., 2020; Zimmerman et al., 2016). According to Oberai (2021), workplace ostracism employees were more likely to engage in counterproductive work behavior and leave their jobs, which could lead to increased organizational costs and turnover. According to the social exchange theory, people weigh their actions and trade resources (Blau, 1964). By preventing an employee from using social resources, workplace ostracism violates the social contract between an employee and an employer (Zimmerman et al., 2016). This could result in feelings of hostility, resentment, counterproductive work behavior, and intention to leave the organization (Murad et al., 2021). If employees feel alienated by their employer, they are more likely to seek work elsewhere. The social identity theory states that belonging to a group affects one's perception of

oneself (Steffens *et al.*, 2021). According to Howard *et al.* (2020), employees bullied at work may experience negative emotions, counterproductive work behavior, and job searching.

H7: The relationship between workplace ostracism and employee retention is mediated by counterproductive work behavior.

Figure 1:
Theoretical Model

METHODOLOGY

Sample and Procedure

The study questionnaire was rigorously tested for accuracy, equivalence, and suitability for native Arabic speakers. The back-to-back method was used for the translation of the questionnaire. Language experts translated the questionnaire to preserve the original questions' meaning. This ensured that all participants understood the questions without language barriers.

The translated questionnaire was pilot tested with a small group to ensure clarity and suitability for the study population.

The data collection process was planned and executed quickly using an online platform to reach a diverse group of participants. Data were gathered in three phases, between October 2022 to February 2023. Demographic and workplace ostracism data were collected first. This phase yielded 568 complete responses. In the second phase, core self-evaluation and counterproductive work behavior data were collected, and 447 of 568 first-phase respondents responded in this phase. The third phase collected employee retention data, and 249 from the second-phase respondents responded in this phase.

Cook and Leverage's outlier test yielded 235 valid responses. Women numbered 83, while the rest were men. 71.9% had one to five years of work experience. Whereas 61.6% of the sample were private sector participants.

Measures

The measurement section of this study utilized a questionnaire as a tool for data collection. The questionnaire consists of five subsections, with the first subsection being demographic. The second subsection assessed workplace ostracism using the Ferris et al. (2008) developed scale. Participants were asked to rate each statement, for example, "others ignored you at work," based on how often they felt the sentiment. The average variance explained for the workplace ostracism scale was 0.539, indicating scale validity (Table 1).

The third subsection assessed counterproductive work behavior by using the 12-item scale developed by Dalal et al. (2009). The participants were asked to rate each statement on a Likert 5-point scale (1=never to 5=always), for example, "spent time on tasks unrelated to work," based on how often they engaged in the listed behavior. The average variance explained for the counterproductive work behavior scale was 0.548, indicating scale validity (Table 1). Six items were removed from the counterproductive work behavior analysis because of low factor loading (value < 0.4).

The fourth subsection assessed core self-evaluation, and the 12-item scale was developed. Judge (2003). Participants were asked to rate each statement on a five-point Likert scale (1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly agree), for example, "I feel confident handling personal problems,". The average variance explained for the core self-evaluation scale was 0.579,

indicating scale validity (Table 1). Six items were removed from the core self-evaluation analysis because of low factor loading (value < 0.4).

The fifth subsection assessed employee retention using four items scale developed by Mobley et al. (1978). Participants were asked to rate each statement on a five-point Likert scale (1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly agree), for example, "If I wanted to do another job or function, I would look first at the possibilities within this organization". The average variance explained for the employee retention scale was 0.526, indicating scale validity (Table 1).

The researchers employed the method Dijkstra and Henseler (2015) recommended to evaluate the reliability and validity of the reflective constructs. Overall, the measurement tools used in this study proved to be reliable, valid, and relevant for measuring the constructs of interest in the study. The Cronbach's alpha, rho-a, and composite reliability values for the workplace ostracism (0.921, 0.925, 0.933), counterproductive work behavior (0.795, 0.797, 0.850), core self-evaluation (0.769, 0.772, 0.835), and employee retention (0.735, 0.739, 0.816) were found to be in an acceptable range. This suggests that the constructs are reliable and that the items measure the same underlying construct. The results show that all constructs have acceptable loadings, ranging from 0.461 to 0.878, meeting the recommended criteria of 0.40 or higher. Multicollinearity was evaluated utilizing the variance inflation factor (VIF). VIF values range between (1.247) and (2.554), which is well below the threshold of 3 (Table 1). This indicates that the items used to measure each construct appropriately capture the underlying concepts. Therefore, the measurement model is appropriate for the subsequent analysis of the relationships between the constructs.

Table 1: Descriptive and Correlation Statistics

	Descriptive Statistics		Pearson Correlation Analysis			
	Mean	SD	WO	CSE	CWB	ER
Workplace Ostracism	1.654	0.441	1.000			
Core Self-Evaluation	4.397	0.381	-0.402**	1.000		
Counterproductive Work Behavior	1.604	0.407	0.506**	-0.608**	1.000	
Employee Retention	4.344	0.394	-0.377**	0.714**	-0.572**	1.000

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Common Method Variance

According to Podsakoff et al. (2012), researchers used procedural and statistical methods to avoid method discrimination. The study used these methods to reduce the impact of single-source data. To reduce social desirability bias, respondents were assured of data confidentiality and anonymity. During the questionnaire design, independent and dependent variables were separated and distributed in separate phases.

Harman's single-factor test was run on all variables' items using principal component analysis to examine common method variance (Gannon et al., 2021). The unrotated principal component analysis identified four factors in the data. One factor explained 30.438% of the variance, and the study's main factors explained 65.535%, below the 40% threshold. Hair et al. (2020) says this study does not have CMV.

DATA ANALYSIS

The researchers in the study used a statistical approach called partial least squares-structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) to evaluate their theoretical framework and perform path analysis. PLS-SEM is a useful tool for social science research because it can address measurement issues that may arise, especially when dealing with multiple latent variables. SEM is a research method that helps to identify and analyze causal relationships between variables. It can adjust for observed variable imprecision when working with latent variable constructs. This means that the researchers could examine the connections between observed and latent variables while accounting for any discrepancies in the data.

Results

Table 2 presents the mean, standard deviation, and Pearson correlation of the variables under investigation. This information provides an overview of the collected data and helps identify any patterns or relationships between the variables. The mean and standard deviations of the variables explain that respondents have low workplace ostracism and counterproductive work behavior, whereas they exhibit high core self-evaluation and employee retention. The Pearson correlation statistics in Table 2 show that core self-evaluation has the strongest and most positive relation with ER ($r = 0.714^{**}$), while negative relation with counterproductive work behavior ($r = -0.608^{**}$).

Table 2: Assessment of Reflective Measurement

Constructs	Items	Type	Loadings	CA	rho-A	CR	AVE	VIF
Workplace Ostracism	WO1	Reflective	0.747	0.921	0.925	0.933	0.539	1.849
	WO2		0.734					1.581
	WO3		0.794					1.866
	WO4		0.767					1.856
	WO5		0.751					2.113
	WO6		0.826					2.356
	WO7		0.832					2.554
	WO8		0.843					1.693
	WO9		0.871					1.437
	WO10		0.804					1.565
	WO11		0.808					1.616
	WO12		0.841					1.605
	WO13		0.878					1.388
Counterproductive Work Behavior	CWB1	Reflective	0.832	0.795	0.797	0.850	0.548	2.247
	CWB2		0.833					1.443
	CWB3		0.831					1.431
	CWB6		0.822					2.074
	CWB9		0.616					2.288
	CWB10		0.733					2.029
	CWB12		0.620					1.398
Core Self-Evaluation	CSE1	Reflective	0.557	0.769	0.772	0.835	0.579	1.324
	CSE3		0.502					1.38
	CSE4		0.461					1.581
	CSE8		0.462					1.503

	CSE10		0.429					1.238
	CSE11		0.538					1.287
	CSE12		0.594					1.405
	ER1		0.526	0.735	0.739	0.816	0.526	1.307
Employee Retention	ER2	Reflective	0.510					1.302
	ER3		0.604					1.424
	ER4		0.465					1.247

Note: CA= Cronbach Alpha; CR = Composite Reliability; AVE = Average Variance Extracted; VIF = Variance Inflation Factor

Discriminant Validity

Two criteria assessed the discriminant validity of the study's four constructs (workplace ostracism, counterproductive work behavior, core self-evaluation, and employee retention). The first was the Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) ratio, which compared how the constructs correlated with each other and themselves. The constructs were not unique if the values exceeded 0.90 (Henseler et al., 2015).

The second criterion, the Fornell-Larcker criterion, compared the variance each construct explained to its correlation with other constructs (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). The bold diagonal numbers showed how much variance each construct explained, while the other numbers showed their correlation. A construct's variance was unique if it was higher than its correlation. Table 3 shows that all constructs had higher variance values than their correlation with other constructs, indicating that each construct was unique and distinct.

Table 3: Discriminant Analysis (HTMT and Fornell-Larcker Criterion)

	Hetro-Trait Mono-Trait (HTMT) Criterion				Fornell-Larcker Criterion			
	WO	CWB	CSE	ER	WO	CWB	CSE	ER
Workplace Ostracism					0.734			
Counterproductive Work Behavior	0.589				0.507	0.740		
Core Self-Evaluation	0.479	0.771			-0.413	-0.614	0.761	
Employee Retention	0.469	0.733	0.710		-0.385	-0.559	0.672	0.725

Note 1: The bold numbers in diagonal in Fornell- Larcker section are square root of AVE of each construct, and other numbers are correlation between constructs.

Note 2: Workplace Ostracism (WO); Counterproductive Work Behavior (CWB); Core Self-Evaluation (CSE); Employee Retention (ER).

The results of Table 4 indicate that all variables exhibit an SRMR value of 0.081 and an NFI value of 0.929, indicating that the model accurately fits the empirical data. Furthermore, the Q^2_{Predict} values for counterproductive work behavior, core self-evaluation, and employee retention demonstrate high predictive relevance with large effect sizes.

The Q^2_{Predict} values for counterproductive work behavior, core self-evaluation, and employee retention have been 0.357, 0.456, and 0.379, respectively. These Q^2_{Predict} values exceed the recommended minimum threshold of 0.00 and demonstrate the model's good predictive capacity for each variable (Henseler et al., 2009). Additionally, the Q^2 effect sizes for counterproductive work behavior, core self-evaluation, and employee retention are large, indicating that these variables significantly impact the endogenous variable (workplace ostracism).

Table 4: Model Evaluation

Variables	SRMR	NFI	Q^2_{Predict}	Q^2 Effect
Workplace Ostracism				
Counterproductive Work Behavior	0.081	0.929	0.357	Large
Core Self-Evaluation			0.456	Large
Employee Retention			0.379	Large

Note: SRMR (Standardized Root Mean Square Residual); NFI (Normed Fit Index); Q^2_{Predict} for Predictive Relevance

Hypothesis Testing

The results of the hypothesis evaluation are presented in Table 5 and Figure 2. The table provides the results of a path analysis examining the relationships between workplace ostracism, counterproductive work behavior, core self-evaluation, and employee retention. The results suggest that all the proposed hypotheses are supported, with significant direct or indirect effects between the variables.

Table 5: Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Direct / Indirect	Path	T	P	BCCI		Hypothesis Support
	Effect	Coefficients	Value	values	5.00%	95.00%	
H ₁	WO -> ER	-0.337	7.507	0.000	-0.415	-0.240	Supported
H ₂	WO -> CWB	0.507	10.642	0.000	0.395	0.587	Supported
H ₃	WO -> CSE	-0.412	7.518	0.000	-0.503	-0.284	Supported
H ₄	CWB -> ER	-0.235	4.088	0.000	-0.344	-0.120	Supported
H ₅	CSE -> ER	0.528	10.206	0.000	0.420	0.626	Supported
H ₆	CWB -> ER	-0.119	3.638	0.000	-0.186	-0.057	Supported
H ₇	WO -> CSE -> ER	-0.218	5.727	0.000	-0.289	-0.142	Supported

Note: Workplace Ostracism (WO); Counterproductive Work Behavior (CWB); Core Self-Evaluation (CSE); Employee Retention (ER); Bias Corrected Confidence Interval (BCCI)

Specifically, workplace ostracism was found to have a significant negative direct effect on employee retention ($\beta = -0.337$, $p < 0.001$, $t = 7.507$), a significant positive direct effect on counterproductive work behavior ($\beta = 0.507$, $p < 0.001$, $t = 10.642$), and a significant negative direct effect on core self-evaluation ($\beta = -0.412$, $p < 0.001$, $t = 7.518$). Additionally, counterproductive work behavior was found to have a significant negative direct effect on employee retention ($\beta = -0.235$, $p < 0.001$, $t = 4.088$), and core self-evaluation was found to have a significant positive direct effect on employee retention ($\beta = 0.528$, $p < 0.001$, $t = 10.206$).

The product coefficient approach (Indirect effect) was used to calculate the potential mediation impact by evaluating the significance of indirect effects using bias-corrected confidence intervals (BCCI) (Rasoolimanesh et al., 2021). Furthermore, the analysis found that

the indirect effects of workplace ostracism on employee retention through counterproductive work behavior ($\beta = -0.121, p < 0.001, t = 3.638$) and core self-evaluation ($\beta = -0.223, p < 0.001, t = 5.727$) were also significant, indicating that these variables partially mediate the relationship between workplace ostracism and employee retention. Overall, these findings support the importance of workplace ostracism, core self-evaluation, and counterproductive work behavior in shaping employee retention.

Figure 2:
Results: Assessment of Structural Model

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study shed light on the relationship between work ostracism, employee retention, counterproductive work behavior, and core self-evaluations. The study

employed a path analysis approach to examine the direct effects of these variables and utilized the product coefficient approach to assess potential mediating effects.

Firstly, the results indicate that work ostracism has a significant negative direct effect on employee retention. This finding suggests that when employees experience work ostracism, their intention to remain with the organization diminishes. Work ostracism refers to the act of excluding or isolating individuals in the workplace, leading to feelings of exclusion and reduced belongingness. The negative direct effect implies that work ostracism negatively impacts employee retention, potentially leading to higher turnover rates.

Secondly, the study reveals a significant positive direct effect of work ostracism on counterproductive work behavior. This suggests that employees who experience work ostracism are more likely to engage in behaviors that are detrimental to the organization. Work ostracism can elicit negative emotional responses, such as resentment or frustration, which may manifest as counterproductive work behaviors. These behaviors can include intentionally underperforming, spreading rumors, or engaging in acts of sabotage. The positive direct effect highlights the role of work ostracism in fostering counterproductive work behavior among employees.

Furthermore, the findings demonstrate a significant negative direct effect of workplace ostracism on core self-evaluation. This suggests that individuals who experience work ostracism may develop lower levels of positive self-evaluations. Work ostracism can erode an individual's self-worth, self-esteem, and overall evaluation of themselves. The negative direct effect indicates that work ostracism has a detrimental impact on employees' core self-evaluations.

The study also examined the indirect effects of work ostracism on employee retention through the mediating variables of counterproductive work behavior and core self-evaluations. The analysis revealed that these indirect effects were also significant. Specifically, both counterproductive work behavior and core self-evaluation partially mediated the relationship between work ostracism and employee retention.

These findings suggest that work ostracism not only directly affects employee retention but also exerts its influence indirectly through the mediating variables of counterproductive work behavior and core self-evaluations. Employees who experience work ostracism may be more inclined to engage in counterproductive work behaviors and develop negative core self-evaluations, which can contribute to their intention to leave the organization.

IMPLICATIONS

Workplace ostracism or being excluded or ignored by coworkers, can lead to counterproductive work behavior, low core self-evaluation, and lower employee retention (Jahanzeb *et al.*, 2022). It can cause employees anger, resentment, and counterproductive work behavior (Gürlek, 2021). In response to workplace ostracism, employees may engage in counterproductive work behavior. This behavior may also occur because the ostracized employee may feel less invested in the organization and less concerned about their actions (Namubiru, 2023).

Workplace ostracism is excluding an individual from workplace social interactions and relationships, can harm an employee's social exchange with coworkers (Chung, 2020). If employees feel ostracized, they may believe they are not receiving the expected rewards and benefits of being part of the social group at work, which can lead to dissatisfaction and negative emotions (Haldorai *et al.*, 2020; Sarwar *et al.*, 2020). Thus, the employee may use counterproductive work behavior to restore social balance (Sowe & Arslan, 2023). According to social exchange theory, workplace ostracism may hurt employee retention (Iqbal *et al.*, 2022). Employees may leave the organization for better opportunities if they feel their social interactions at work are not being rewarded (Mustafa & Ali, 2019). Thus, organizations must prevent workplace ostracism and encourage employee social interaction. This can include promoting inclusivity and respect, providing social interaction and relationship-building opportunities, and promptly and effectively addressing workplace ostracism. Workplace ostracism can lower core self-evaluation and cause low self-esteem, self-doubt, and inadequacy (Anestis *et al.*, 2022; Zhang *et al.*, 2023). The study found that employees with low core self-evaluation may be more susceptible to the negative effects of ostracism, resulting in lower self-esteem, motivation, and work engagement to balance the exchanges.

In Saudi Arabian organizations, managers should be aware of the potential for ostracism to cause an increase in counterproductive work behavior and negatively influence their core self-evaluation. Therefore, they should take steps to prevent counterproductive work behavior and boost core self-evaluation. This could include creating a culture of inclusion, providing training on effective communication, setting clear expectations for behavior, providing opportunities for employees to develop their skills, recognizing, and rewarding good performance, and creating a positive work environment.

Workplace ostracism can result in low levels of employee retention, which can be costly for organizations. Low retention rates can be particularly concerning for organizations in Saudi Arabia, where loyalty is often valued. To retain employees, managers should prioritize creating a positive work environment that fosters inclusivity and respect, provides competitive compensation, and advantages, and offers career improvement and advancement possibilities. Additionally, providing a supportive work culture can enhance employee satisfaction and retention.

FUTURE DIRECTIONS AND LIMITATIONS

This work has practical and theoretical implications, although it has challenges. Initially, a small sample size was used for this study. Most of the sample size, which determined how broadly the results could be applied, comprised male participants (>70%). Future scholars will benefit greatly from the insights provided by this work. First, it is suggested that future studies follow suit in other sectors, including banks, telecommunication, and hospitals. In this study, preference sampling was employed. Future researchers are advised to employ bigger and more varied sample sizes to ensure study generalizability. Future research could also consider using vertical design, probability, or sample random sampling procedures to reduce general methodological bias. This study's design can be used in different cultures and nations.

CONCLUSION

The study highlights the detrimental impact of work ostracism on employee retention. The findings underscore the need for organizations to address and prevent workplace ostracism, as it can lead to higher turnover rates and negative work behaviors. Additionally, organizations should foster positive core self-evaluations among employees to mitigate the negative effects of work ostracism. By promoting inclusivity, belongingness, and positive social interactions, organizations can create an environment that supports employee retention and well-being.

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